

D6.25 ExPaNDS Photons and Neutrons communities use cases

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Abstract

This document shows the different use cases identified among Photon and Neutron (PaN) facilities by ExPaNDS during the grant period.

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Executive Summary

The Photon and Neutron Research Infrastructures (PaN RIs) across Europe play an important role in scientific research, helping scientists from a wide variety of different disciplines gain deeper insights into major questions in their respective fields. Datasets produced in synchrotrons cover a large variety of format, thus needing a wide variety of analysis tools.

This deliverable describes different case studies that show the large variety of techniques among the PaN facilities, and how ExPaNDS can help scientists to have their data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) and open. These case studies highlight the work realised by several work packages and their complementarity. We present a real publication or dataset for each case study.

ExPaNDS COVID case study: *Diamond Light Source produced a lot of data through the X-Chem fragment screening platform. ExPaNDS helped by suggesting the usage of Zenodo as a data repository for raw data, allowing the community to access and process the data.*

ExPaNDS reflectometry case study: *the researchers work on solid/liquid interface. In this domain, metadata are crucial to allow the reproducibility of data. ExPaNDS can help by minting the DOI, and associating the data, metadata and analysis workflow.*

Tomography case study: *For this use case, the team of researchers is working on the development of bio-chars from waste. This use case was developed specifically for the ExPaNDS project, to show what tasks need to be realised to have open and FAIR data. ExPaNDS aided by helping the researchers in tagging the dataset and analysis workflow using the common ExPaNDS taxonomy, to make them FAIR. This case study allows the researchers to understand how data can be made open to all the community.*

ExPaNDS serial crystallography case study: *serial crystallography is a recent technique that allows collecting information on a macromolecular structure without a need for a large protein crystal. It is particularly helpful for some proteins that can't be crystallised using conventional techniques. One of the bottlenecks of this technique is the production of a large amount of data, up to 150 TB per day. ExPaNDS can help in presenting a reference dataset, and all the analysis workflow.*

ExPaNDS Kinetic SAXS case study: *this technique is a powerful method for the structural characterisation of proteins in solution. It also allows studies in various experimental conditions, and in a time-resolved manner. As such, it is using a huge amount of data storage and needs data reduction to allow sharing to the community. ExPaNDS can help in providing a reduced dataset and the analysis workflow to understand how data reduction and data analysis are done.*

ExPaNDS full field tomography case study: *this imaging technique is widely used in a lot of scientific domains, from life science to physics study. Huge datasets need to be accessible from relevant data landing pages with the matching metadata. ExPaNDS helped by presenting a case study where data was collected at PSI, and where both raw data and the analysis workflow are accessible, allowing reproducibility of the results.*

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ExPaNDS Terahertz spectroscopy case study: *this technique is used mainly in physics, chemistry and material science. Metadata, analysis workflow and calculation process are mandatory to understand all the parameters of the experiment. ExPaNDS can help in helping the facility to implement the data catalogue API, allowing the researchers to identify raw datasets that can be relevant for their study.*

ExPaNDS Neutron small angle scattering case study: *this technique can be used to explore the structure of liquids and solid from various length. One advantage is that the technique is less destructive compared to X-ray SAXS. ExPaNDS helped by identifying a reference dataset, and the analysis pipeline from data reduction, to data analysis.*

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PaN community use cases

ExPaNDS COVID case study

ExPaNDS COVID Case Study

European Open Science Cloud Photon and Neutron Data Services

Description of research:

The COVID Moonshot is a worldwide consortium that include academic and industrial groups, working to identify new compounds that could block the SARS-CoV-2 and develop an antiviral drug that would be safe, affordable and easily-manufactured.

The COVID Moonshot consortium aims to release all the data generated by the project, to help researchers in the discovery of new antivirals molecules against coronaviruses.

At Diamond Light Source (Diamond), the Principal Investigator (PI) for the Moonshot project is Professor Dr Frank von Delft. Diamond helps mainly through the X-Chem fragment screening platform.

Challenge:

The work undertaken by Frank von Delft and his team as part of the Moonshot collaboration consists of the screening of the available fragment libraries at Diamond with crystals of the Main Protease of the COVID-19.

The work has been done in collaboration with the I04-1 Beamline, where data collection has been realised.

The main challenges for this project were:

- The production of a large amount of data sets and associated metadata;
- The analysis of the raw data;
- The release of this FAIR data on to the Zenodo platform, to be accessible and usable by the MX community.

How can ExPaNDS help?

- A large amount of data has been created and analysed, before being released into the Protein Data Bank (PDB). PDB identification is used as PID.
- ExPaNDS suggested the usage of Zenodo as a data repository for raw diffraction data of proteins, allowing the community to access and process the data at will.
- A clear example of the good usage of Zenodo to serve a specific problem or community and ExPaNDS identified it possible solution for some of the national facilities that cannot afford a data catalogue of their own.
- Zenodo is a practical solution to find data. In this case, Zenodo data are linked to PDB data to maximise to dissemination of information. There is a potential further maximisation of Zenodo through direct involvement in the development direction of the tool.

Publication link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3730531>

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ExPaNDS reflectometry case study

Description of research:

Dr McCluskey et al. were interested in the structure of phospholipid monolayers at the surface of a novel Deep Eutectic Solvent (DES). They were able to collect a series of X-ray reflectometry data. However the analysis could not rely on the usual assumptions made about these materials previously measured on water.

Challenge:

Dr McCluskey's published results include a fully reproducible workflow available on GitHub and Zenodo. However, the reprocessing of this data requires intensive computing and as such this resource is not really used for the intended purpose. If this method of open and reproducible publication is to become commonplace then data needs to be easily extractable and reproducible by all.

Reflectometry is a model dependent technique and as such, information about the sample under investigation is crucial to the analysis of experimental data.

The models are usually based on three parameters accounting for the density, roughness and thickness of layers at an interface. Typically the starting values are a mixture of sample knowledge, published results and trail and error.

Reflectometry publications have traditionally struggled to publish sufficient information about samples to allow

the results to be fully reproducible. This is particularly true for delicate soft-matter samples that are prepared during experiments at air-liquid or solid-liquid interfaces.

Recent efforts from the community have led to the establishment of the Open Reflectometry Standards Organisation (ORSO) which is attempting to standardise file formats, data collection, reduction and analysis methodologies across both synchrotron and neutron large facilities.

How can ExPaNDS help?

ExPaNDS can help by:

- minting a DOI for the dataset and offering a data landing page where authorised users can download the dataset;
- associating the dataset, publication and analysis workflow and having each of them referencing the other using persistent identifier;
- tagging the dataset and analysis workflow application using the common ExPaNDS taxonomy to make the elements easier to find by interested parties;
- making the data findable via the common search API (and FAIR) and available in EOSC Cloud;
- explore options around the publishing and long term preservation of data & best practice in open science.

ORSO website: www.reflectometry.org

Publication link: <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9CP00203K>
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Tomography case study

Tomography Case Study

ExPaNDS
European Open Science Cloud Photon
and Neutron Data Services

Description of research:

Dr Roberto Volpe and his team are working on the development of bio-chars from agricultural waste (almond and walnut shells). Such chars represent renewable and inexpensive solutions to a variety of morphology dependent challenges such as air, water, and soil treatment, catalysis, and energy storage.

Biochar can improve water quality, reduce soil emissions of greenhouse gases, reduce nutrient leaching, reduce soil acidity and reduce irrigation and fertilizer requirements.

Challenge:

The work undertaken by Dr Volpe and his team at Diamond Light Source on Beamline I13 is generating a large quantity of valuable *in-situ* radiography and tomography data. Additionally, the team is developing custom applications built with MatLab to perform the analysis of the data collected.

The size limit of Zenodo's data set however means that it is not possible for the team to make the data open in the same manner. As a result, the raw data is available to peers upon request to the Principal Investigator (PI) and transfers are done manually using commercial services (e.g dropbox).

How can ExPaNDS help?

- minting a DOI for the dataset and offering a data landing page where authorised users can download the dataset;
- associating the dataset, publication and analysis workflow and having each of them referencing the other using persistent identifier;
- tagging the dataset and analysis workflow application using the common ExPaNDS taxonomy to make the elements easier to find by interested parties;
- making the data findable via the common search API (and FAIR) and available in EOSC Cloud;
- test the value of common search APIs/sample data sets for FAIR commercial use case together with Thermo Fisher;
- allow for community engagement to gain collaborators to work on the data analysis;
- explore options around the publishing and long term preservation of data;
- supporting the Science team in using best practice for open science.

Reconstructed and segmented tomograms and corresponding three-dimensional (3-D) renderings of raw and pyrolysed water soaked almond shells. Pyrolysed shells were heated at a rate of $6^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ to a final temperature of 450°C and held for 30 min. In 3-D renderings, the scale bar corresponds to the frontmost plane.

Publications presenting the work and results are published in open access journals. The custom applications have been published on Zenodo to allow for free and open access of the analysis package.

Publication link: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-020-80228-x#data-availability>

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ExPaNDS Serial Crystallography case study

The PaN community is extremely diverse covering virtually all scientific fields of research. This is a challenge when developing data pipelines and to make them meaningful in catalogues. It's become clear that data needs lot of contextualisation for data mining to be successful. The most successful communities are those who already have bespoke data catalogues where facilities can feed their data pipeline to be displayed within a wider context.

The ExPaNDS grant has allowed detailed mapping of the data pipelines to understand the extent to which the FAIR principles have been deployed and how the chosen community made their data open.

Description of technique:

Serial crystallography is a beamline technique for collecting information on the structure of a protein without growing large protein crystals. Instead, a large number of small protein crystals are held in a pulsed X-ray beam.

The development of serial femtosecond crystallography (SFX) has opened up new avenues for the measurement of macromolecular structures and macromolecular dynamics. This technique allows room-temperature measurements using micrometer-sized and smaller protein crystals, damage free determination of radiation sensitive structures, and time-resolved studies of biomolecular dynamics at physiologically relevant temperatures.

Challenge:

- Experiments generate up to 150 TB per day of data saved at the measurement facility. Such large datasets are impractical for users to take home.
- File format varies according to facility and instrument. Could be XTC files (LCLS), HD5 files (Eiger) or CBF files (Pilatus).
- The dataset presented here are realised using microcrystals of hen egg white lysozyme. The size of the raw data is 10TB, and the reduced data containing hits is 79 GB. Access to a virtual desktop for intermediate file access is mandatory, unless a specific workflow is produced

How can ExPaNDS help?

ExPaNDS exposed the technical challenges for facilities to implement the data catalogue APIs developed under the PANOSC grant. Some facilities across Europe are clearly more advanced on this than others and a mixed approach is required for progress to be made.

- ExPaNDS helps by presenting a dataset example using Lysozyme microcrystal as a use case for Serial Crystallography technique (<https://cxidb.org/id-98.html>). The dataset are available on CXIDB, a depository specific for XFEL data with relevant metadata.
- This use case is presented on the Pan-training portal developed by ExPaNDS and PaNOSC, where training courses and analysis workflow resources are available (raw data, reduced data, CrysFEL container, git lab resources)

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ExPaNDS Kinetic SAXS case study

ExPaNDS Kinetic SAXS Case Study

ExPaNDS

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The PaN community is extremely diverse covering virtually all scientific fields of research. This is a challenge when developing data pipelines and to make them meaningful in catalogues. It's become clear that data needs lot of contextualisation for data mining to be successful. The most successful communities are those who already have bespoke data catalogues where facilities can feed their data pipeline to be displayed within a wider context.

The ExPaNDS grant has allowed detailed mapping of the data pipelines to understand the extent to which the FAIR principles have been deployed and how the chosen community made their data open.

Description of technique:

- Small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) is a powerful method for the structural characterisation of both ordered and disordered proteins in solution. It provides information about the sizes and shapes of proteins and complexes in a broad range of molecular sizes ranging from a few kDa to GDa and under various experimental conditions varying from extreme (e.g. high pressure or cryo-frozen) to nearly native.
- SAXS, especially using high intensity synchrotron sources, is a rapid technique and time-resolved studies yield unique information about kinetics of processes and interactions.

Technical challenge:

- Cartography or kinetic experiments can generate up to 3 TB per day of raw data saved at the measurement facility. Such large datasets are impractical for users to take home. Subsequent analysis needs to be performed remotely on a performant platform, making it attractive for deployment as a cloud-like use case. Even for a smaller amount of data, the possibility to perform offline analysis remotely is very attractive, for mail-in and remote-control experiments, which were developed during the sanitary crisis.

Analysis pipeline:

- Raw data are saved by the facility using a series of Nexus files (HD5). All experimental metadata are in the raw data files
- In this use case, data have been reduced and analysed using the Foxtrot software. This software will convert the stacks of raw images into stacks of physically meaningful parameters, according to the specific analysis that has to be performed
- The dataset presented here is a SAXS lmax map from shaped gold nanoparticles (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4553506>)

How can ExPaNDS help?

- The grant provided time and resource for in depth analysis of the current state of data plans. One key conclusion is that the level of implementation of the FAIR principles within these diverse communities is very disparate. The detailed mapping allows for options to be considered when making data available from facilities being ready to implement the data catalogue APIs to those where resources are extremely limited with the option to deposit data onto third party platform like Zenodo or university-based data catalogues.
- For this use case, it was identified that although the data was made available on Zenodo, this is not a sustainable way of cataloguing heavy data sets. There is a need to identify as part of future collaboration better solutions. The grant enabled to build the case for national facilities and advocate the need for community-based portals that can adequately contextualise the data sets.
- ExPaNDS helps by presenting a dataset example using shaped gold nanoparticles as a use case for Kinetic SAXS.
- The reduced dataset can be found on Zenodo: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4553506>
- The site pan-training.eu, developed by ExPaNDS and PaNOSC, proposes an analysis workflow for SAXS experiments.

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ExPaNDS Full Field Tomography case study

ExPaNDS Full field tomography Case Study

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The ExPaNDS grant has allowed detailed mapping of the data pipelines to understand the extent to which the FAIR principles have been deployed and how the chosen community made their data open.

Description of technique:

Full field tomography is a well established and widely used imaging technique. Synchrotron full field tomography allows the imaging of specimens with high resolution in space (3D) and time (4D).

There is a large variety of specimens and imaging applications used predominantly in medical sciences, material research and archeology.

Challenge:

- Tomography datasets often present large volumes (100 GBs to a few TBs in size), which are difficult to be compressed and transferred.

Imaging of a complete intact postmortem juvenile rat lung

- The tomographic reconstruction is highly demanding on computer (GPU) and storage resources for the intermediate and/or final result. In addition, the optional image segmentation step may be demanding on computer memory.
- The offline analysis (after an experiment) may be performed remotely by the user/s potentially at home, making it attractive for deployment as a cloud-like use case.

How ExPaNDS can help?

The grant provided time and resource for in depth analysis of the current state of data plans. One key conclusion is that the level of implementation of the FAIR principles within these diverse communities is very disparate. The detailed mapping allows for options to be considered when making data available from facilities being ready to implement the data catalogue APIs to those where resources are extremely limited with the option to deposit data onto third party platform like Zenodo or university-based data catalogues.

ExPaNDS exposed the technical challenges for facilities to implement the data catalogue APIs developed under the PANOSC grant. Some facilities across Europe are clearly more advanced on this than others and a mixed approach is required for progress to be made.

- ExPaNDS helps by presenting a dataset example using imaging of a use case for full field tomography, (D4.2) which can then be used to test the data analysis service. The dataset is available on the PSI public data repository with some elements of context regarding the experiment done.
- This use case is presented on the PaN-training portal, which has been developed by ExPaNDS, where different training courses and analysis workflows are available for review.

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ExPaNDS Terahertz Spectroscopy case study

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The PaN community is extremely diverse covering virtually all scientific fields of research. This is a challenge when developing data pipelines and to make them meaningful in catalogues. It's become clear that data needs lot of contextualisation for data mining to be successful. The most successful communities are those who already have bespoke data catalogues where facilities can feed their data pipeline to be displayed within a wider context.

The ExPaNDS grant has allowed detailed mapping of the data pipelines to understand the extent to which the FAIR principles have been deployed and how the chosen community made their data open.

Description of technique:

Nonlinear Terahertz (THz) Spectroscopy has developed into a prosperous field of basic research in physics, chemistry and material science. In high energy physics, the Higgs field couples to gauge bosons and fermions and gives masse to their elementary excitations. In this use case THz spectroscopy is used to investigate unconventional superconductivity in cuprates.

Challenge:

THz spectroscopy datasets often present large volumes (100 GBs to a few TBs) which are difficult to compress and transfer. Metadata, analysis workflow and calculation process are mandatory to understand all the parameters of the experiment to allow reproducibility.

Schematic of the ELBE beamline. Electron for beams with High Brilliance and low Emittance. Credits : HZDR

The offline analysis (after an experiment) could be performed remotely by users at home making it attractive for deployment as a cloud-like use case.

How can ExPaNDS help?

- The grant provided time and resource for in depth analysis of the current state of data plans. One key conclusion is that the level of implementation of the FAIR principles within these diverse communities is very disparate. The detailed mapping allows for options to be considered when making data available from facilities being ready to implement the data catalogue APIs to those where resources are extremely limited with the option to deposit data onto third party platform like Zenodo or university-based data catalogues.
- ExPaNDS exposed the technical challenges for facilities to implement the data catalogue APIs developed under the PANOSC grant. Some facilities across Europe are clearly more advanced on this than others and a mixed approach is required for progress to be made.
- ExPaNDS helps by presenting a dataset example using superconducting cuprates as a use case for THz spectroscopy technique. The dataset is available on RODARE, a public depository developed by HZDR (<https://rodare.hzdr.de/record/277>).
- This use case is presented on the Pan-training portal developed by ExPaNDS and PaNOSC, where training courses and analysis workflows are available on Jupyter notebooks.

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ExPaNDS Neutron Small Angle Scattering case study

ExPaNDS Neutron Small Angle Scattering Case Study

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European Open Science Cloud Photon and Neutron Data Services

The PaN community is extremely diverse covering virtually all scientific fields of research. This is a challenge when developing data pipelines and to make them meaningful in catalogues. It's become clear that data needs lot of contextualisation for data mining to be successful. The most successful communities are those who already have bespoke data catalogues where facilities can feed their data pipeline to be displayed within a wider context.

The ExPaNDS grant has allowed detailed mapping of the data pipelines to understand the extent to which the FAIR principles have been deployed and how the chosen community made their data open.

Description of technique:

Neutron small angle scattering explores the mesostructures of liquids and solids on length scales ranging from 1 nanometre to about a micron. These include polymers, alloys, and biological macromolecules. This technique offers significant advantages compared to other probes. Neutrons are less destructive than other forms of radiation, such as X-rays, as they do not damage sensitive biological samples, and they can be used to detect magnetic properties thanks to their magnetic moment.

The dataset for the technique was part of an investigation into creating a new protein standard for protein small angle scattering (SAS).

Analysis pipeline:

- The first step is *data reduction*. For this you can use the software Mantid: this data reduction software is adopted at every neutron facility. It allows you to turn raw data into reduced data, which can be used for analysis. (<https://www.mantidproject.org/>)
- The second step is *data analysis*. Different approaches exist, depending on the data that you want to analyse.

- For the dataset presented in this case study, there is a specific jupyter notebook provided to reduce and analyse the data presented within the publication.

How can ExPaNDS help?

For this use case, it was identified that although the data was made available on GitHub, this is not a sustainable way of cataloguing heavy data sets. There is a need to identify as part of future collaboration better solutions. The grant enabled to build the case for national facilities and advocate the need for community-based portals that can adequately contextualise the data sets.

- ExPaNDS helps by presenting a dataset example using the GFP monomer as a use case for Neutron Small Angle Scattering.
- The publication of Myatt et al (2017, 10.3233/BSI-170167) included a dataset which can be used for Neutron Small Angle Scattering.
- The github link provides a jupyter notebook showcasing the workflow for data reduction.
- The site PaN-learning.org proposes training and courses on Neutron Scattering theory and data analysis workflows which are available on pan-training.eu platform.

Fig 1: The crystal structure of the GFP monomer

Fig 2: SANS curves of 3 different concentrations of GFP

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Summary

This deliverable highlights different case studies identified during the ExPaNDS project. It shows the large variety of techniques among the PaN facilities, and how ExPaNDS can help scientists to have their data FAIR and open. Amongst the challenges identified, the main issue is the incredibly large size of datasets, which can't be shared easily. Reduction workflow and analysis workflow must be shared with all the others metadata for each dataset. For these case studies, data analysis workflows were created on the PaN training portal (<https://pan-training.eu/>) by different work packages of ExPaNDS (WP4 and WP5). Other issues such as dataset availability through a data portal, and description of metadata (relevant to WP2 and WP3) are also addressed.

